

Copula-based joint distributions of rain and wind for leading edge erosion risk atlas

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ABSTRACT

Evaluating the risk of leading edge erosion on wind turbine blades requires accurate characterization of wind and rain climates, as they determine the amount of rain impinging the blades. However, existing fatigue lifetime models often assume statistical independence between wind speed and rain intensity, potentially underestimating erosion risks. This study introduces a copula-based framework to explicitly model their dependence using historical data from the British Isles and surrounding seas. The methodology is used to generate a probabilistic erosion parameter atlas containing site-specific marginal distributions and copula parameters. The parameter atlas enables fast and tailored estimates of the probabilistic incubation period, allowing for site-specific reliability analysis based on custom turbine operation characteristics and blade coating materials. The framework also supports the assessment of erosion-safe operation feasibility by quantifying the trade-off between fatigue life extension and energy production loss. Results reveal that neglecting the dependence structure can lead to overestimation of the incubation period by up to 90% in regions where the wind–rain correlation is high, particularly in offshore and coastal areas. A clear positive correlation between wind speed and rain intensity is observed, with the effect being even more pronounced in dry conditions, where wind speed on average is 50% higher when it rains 10 mm/hr compared to no rain, highlighting the critical need to incorporate wind–rain dependence into erosion risk assessments.

1. Introduction

In recent years, there has been a significant transition towards more renewable energy. Here, wind energy has emerged as a cornerstone for this transformation, offering a clean and universal energy source. The commitment to renewable energy, stems from the urgent need to reduce greenhouse gas emissions, mitigate climate change, and ensure a sustainable future [1]. The operation and maintenance expenses of a wind farm usually make up 20%–30% of the overall lifetime cost [2]. This percentage varies depending on several factors, including the location and size of the wind farm, the type of turbines installed, and the specific maintenance strategy.

With the growing employment of wind farms in diverse environments, both onshore and offshore, wind turbines are increasingly exposed to a variety of environmental conditions that can affect their efficiency and lifespan. Among these is leading edge erosion (LEE) which occurs when the turbine blades are exposed to repeated impacts from rain, hail, and airborne particles at high velocities. These repeated collisions create tiny pits and cracks on the blade surfaces, gradually worsening over time [3]. LEE can have serious impact on both efficiency and maintenance, as it reduces aerodynamic performance and requires more frequent servicing to prevent structural issues [4].

The development of rain erosion on wind turbine blades is primarily governed by two environmental factors, namely the rain and wind climates. While summary statistics of these variables can serve as useful proxies, it is the combination of rain and the velocity at which droplets strike the blade surface that fundamentally drives the erosion rate [5]. As an example, a prolonged period of heavy rain without wind would cause minimal erosion damage, similar to what high winds without rain would. When intense wind and rain co-occur, the high-energy collisions of the rain drops with the blade can rapidly accelerate the onset and progression of leading edge erosion. Consequently, this co-occurrence of wind and rain is a critical factor to accurately model the leading edge erosion.

Estimating and forecasting leading edge erosion accurately remains an extremely difficult challenge. Even the blades on the same turbine can experience significantly different erosion behavior. The stochastic process can be attributed to the complex and variable environmental conditions but also uncertainty in material properties. In addition, there is a need to distinguish between the incubation period (time to the initial breakthrough of protective coatings) and the levels of erosion defects, which vary in type, severity, and extent [6]. While the

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incubation period indicates the onset time of the damage, the following erosion stages involve a variety of defects, from surface pitting to severe material loss, each with different implications for turbine performance and maintenance/repair strategies.

Several probabilistic modeling approaches have been introduced, trying to capture some of this inherent variability, primarily related to weather exposure. These approaches typically rely on univariate probability distributions to independently represent wind speed and rain intensity for fatigue life estimation [7]. This modeling framework enables site-specific lifetime prediction based on marginal distributions, even when only unsynchronized or separately recorded datasets are available [8,9]. Recent studies have further extended this methodology toward reliability analysis and integration into O&M planning frameworks [10,11]. Despite its practicality and wide adoption in both academia and industry, this modeling strategy assumes independence between wind and rain, which may not reflect real-world environmental conditions. Neglecting the dependence structure can oversimplify erosion lifetime predictions and lead to systematic misinterpretation of site-specific erosion risks [12].

A direct way to incorporate wind–rain dependence is through time series analysis, where historical weather data is analyzed to capture co-occurring wind and rain conditions. This method provides a realistic representation without requiring explicit dependency modeling and has been successfully applied for site-specific erosion risk assessments, e.g., using global precipitation products from satellites [13,14] and for large-scale erosion atlases, covering areas such as Scandinavia [15] and the British Isles [16]. However, time series analysis typically requires access to continuous, high-quality historical weather data (measurements and/or reanalysis), which may be unavailable for many locations or sufficiently long periods. Accounting for different turbine types, operational characteristics or blade material properties might also be inefficient to evaluate through time series analysis. Similarly, generating uncertainty estimates within this framework would likely rely on resampling methods, such as bootstrapping, which can be computationally expensive and may still fail to capture the full range of rare, high-impact events accurately.

An alternative approach is to use copula-based modeling, which explicitly captures the joint dependency structure between random variables, such as wind speed and rain intensity [17]. Copulas have been widely applied in multi-hazard assessments, such as for civil infrastructure [18], crop lodging [19] or typhoons [20], but their potential for wind turbine erosion modeling has not been explored. Unlike time series analysis, copulas can be used to generate probabilistic joint distributions. This flexibility makes them well-suited for erosion modeling, as they allow for site-specific probabilistic assessments while overcoming the data limitations of direct time series approaches. By incorporating wind–rain dependence explicitly, copula-based models enable more accurate risk assessments and provide a foundation for evaluating erosion-safe operational strategies within a probabilistic framework.

In this study, we demonstrate how copulas can be used to capture the statistical dependence between random variables, namely wind speed and rain intensity. We show the importance of including the statistical dependence between wind and rain for the leading edge erosion modeling. The obtained fitting parameters will serve as the foundation for a probabilistic erosion risk atlas which has several applications. Firstly, it can be used to quickly assess site-specific climatic conditions relevant for modeling leading edge erosion on wind turbine blades, including marginal and conditional statistics and distributions. Secondly, the erosion parameter atlas facilitates rapid, probabilistic assessments of blade erosion risks based on local wind turbine operational conditions and coating material properties, which can also be expressed probabilistically to allow for reliability analysis. Finally, the erosion parameter atlas can be used to evaluate the site-specific efficiency of erosion-safe operation based on power stop-loss or target lifetime.

The structure of the paper is as follows: Section 2 describes the copula-based approach to capturing dependence between wind and rain, Section 3 details the data and methodology used in the study, and Section 4 presents the results, which are further discussed in Section 5.

2. Constructing joint distribution using copulas

The cumulative distribution function (CDF), $F_X(x)$, describes the probability that a random variable X takes on a value less than or equal to x :

$$F_X(x) = P(X \leq x) \quad (1)$$

where P denotes the probability operator. For continuous random variables, the CDF is the integral of the probability density function (PDF), $f_X(x)$, which gives the likelihood that X will take on a specific value:

$$F_X(x) = \int_{-\infty}^x f_X(t) dt \quad (2)$$

For two random variables, X and Y , the joint cumulative distribution function (JCDF), $F_{X,Y}(x, y)$, describes the probability that both X and Y take on values less than or equal to x and y , respectively:

$$F_{X,Y}(x, y) = P(X \leq x, Y \leq y) \quad (3)$$

The joint CDF encompasses both the marginal behavior of each variable and the dependence between them. However, expressing this dependence explicitly in terms of joint PDFs or CDFs can be complex. A copula is a mathematical tool used to couple multivariate joint distributions through their marginals. Sklar's theorem [21,22], states that any multivariate joint distribution can be expressed in terms of its marginals and a copula function. For two random variables X and Y , Sklar's theorem can be written as:

$$F_{X,Y}(x, y) = C(F_X(x), F_Y(y)) \quad (4)$$

where C is the copula function, and $F_X(x)$, $F_Y(y)$ are the marginal CDFs of X and Y , respectively.

The copula function captures the dependence between X and Y , while the marginal distributions F_X and F_Y describe the behavior of each variable individually. This separation of marginals and dependence structure is a major advantage of copulas. In our study, wind speed and rain intensity are often modeled as statistically dependent variables, and copulas offer a powerful approach to capture this dependence without assuming specific forms for the marginal distributions.

The copula density function is the derivative of the copula function with respect to its arguments. Given two random variables X and Y with marginal CDFs $F_X(x)$ and $F_Y(y)$, and a joint CDF $F_{X,Y}(x, y)$, the corresponding copula function $C(U, V)$, where $U = F_X(x)$ and $V = F_Y(y)$, satisfies the relationship:

$$F_{X,Y}(x, y) = C(F_X(x), F_Y(y)) = C(U, V) \quad (5)$$

The copula density function, denoted $c(U, V)$, is the derivative of the copula function $C(U, V)$ with respect to both arguments U and V :

$$c(U, V) = \frac{\partial^2 C(U, V)}{\partial U \partial V} \quad (6)$$

The actual joint density function of X and Y , denoted $f_{X,Y}(x, y)$, can be expressed in terms of the copula density and the marginal density functions $f_X(x)$ and $f_Y(y)$ as follows:

$$f_{X,Y}(x, y) = c(F_X(x), F_Y(y)) \cdot f_X(x) \cdot f_Y(y) \quad (7)$$

The parameters of the copula function can be estimated using different approaches but most commonly is the maximum likelihood estimation (MLE). It works by defining a likelihood function that describes the probability of observing the given data under a set of model parameters. The parameters that maximize this likelihood function are considered the best estimates, as they are the most likely to have generated the observed data. In this study, we use a pseudo-MLE technique where the parameters of univariate marginal distributions are obtained initially and the copula parameter subsequently. The sequential use of MLE for both steps allows for more robust parametric fitting. This

Fig. 1. Visualization of the relationship between a point in copula space (lower left) and its corresponding point in physical space (upper right). The transformation between these spaces is achieved using the marginal distributions of wind speed (upper left) and rain intensity (lower right).

approach ensures that the marginal distributions are accurately fitted before estimating the dependence structure, reducing the potential for bias in the copula parameters.

After fitting both the marginal distributions and the copula function, we can easily transform between the copula space (the probability integral transform space) and the physical space (the original wind speed and rain intensity variables). The copula function is defined by the probability integral transform, where each marginal distribution is transformed into a uniform distribution on the interval [0, 1]. Specifically, each random variable is transformed into a probability value, such that the wind speed and rain intensity are mapped to corresponding values on the x- and y-axes in the uniform space. Once the data points are in the copula space (which is uniform), we can manipulate or sample these uniform values to generate the joint distribution.

Fig. 1 illustrates this process with an example of wind speed and rain intensity as the two random variables, modeled using a Frank copula. The lower-left subfigure visualizes a point in the copula space, where the values are associated with the probability integral transformed rain intensity on the x-axis and wind speed on the y-axis. These values represent the uniform transformations of the original variables. To transform back into the physical space (upper-right subfigure), we apply the inverse of the cumulative distribution function (CDF) for each marginal distribution, which maps the uniform values back to the original physical quantities (wind speed and rain intensity). By sampling in the copula space, we can generate a joint distribution that accurately captures the dependency structure between the two variables, reflecting their true relationship in the physical space.

3. Data and methods

The following section describes the data used for this study and the methodologies for the lifetime calculations and erosion-safe operation.

3.1. Wind and precipitation data

The weather data used in the present study is extracted from two different data products. The New European Wind Atlas (NEWA) is a high-resolution wind resource data product developed for wind energy

research and industry [23]. It provides detailed wind data across Europe, covering complex terrain, offshore regions, and a wide range of atmospheric conditions. The spatial resolution is approximately 3 km × 3 km with a 30 min temporal resolution.

The Integrated Multi-satellite Retrievals for GPM (IMERG) is a high-resolution precipitation data product from NASA’s Global Precipitation Measurement (GPM) mission [24]. IMERG integrates data from multiple satellites to provide near-real-time and research-quality estimates of global precipitation. The spatial resolution is 0.1° × 0.1° (10 km × 10 km), offering detailed global precipitation measurements at a temporal resolution of 30 min. We use the Final Run (IMERG-F) version 07, which has undergone quality control using monthly gauge adjustments [25]. The IMERG precipitation data also comes with a measure of the probability of liquid precipitation, which reflects the likelihood that the recorded precipitation is in a liquid state; higher values correspond to a greater chance of liquid precipitation. We use a filter for this (> 75%) that ensures only liquid precipitation to be included [26]. In addition, we use a threshold (> 0.4) on the supplied quality index to ensure reliable precipitation estimates [27].

Historical data is extracted from the two data products for the period January 2020 to December 2024, thereby providing five full, consecutive years of 30 min samples. The data is extracted across a domain covering the British Isles and the surrounding seas, and the two data products are time- and space-synchronized. Since the NEWA data comes at a finer grid resolution, it is scaled to match the resolution of the IMERG precipitation data. The total number of coordinates included in the two datasets is 15,600 (120 in the latitudinal and 130 in the longitudinal direction). The wind speed from NEWA is extracted at three model level heights, namely 75, 100 and 150 m, whereas the IMERG precipitation data is assumed to be representative of surface conditions, although in reality it is measured at a certain height in the atmosphere.

3.2. Rain impingement and lifetime calculations

The rain impingement is a metric used to describe the amount of water impacting the blade, i.e., equivalent to the amount of rain a virtual gauge would catch if it was placed on a rotating blade [28]. The rain

impingement is based on the droplet impact which comprises the rain, wind, and turbine characteristics. Consequently, rain impingement has been deemed a good metric as a global predictor for erosion [29–31]. The instantaneous rain impingement H can then simply be expressed as:

$$H = W \cdot V_{\text{impact}} \quad (8)$$

where V_{impact} is the relative impact velocity of the droplets. The rotational speed of the wind turbine blades is typically the major contributor to the impact velocity and is therefore a function of the wind speed U . The rain volume concentration in the air, W , is a function of rain intensity I and drop fall velocity V_{droplet} :

$$W = I/V_{\text{droplet}} \quad (9)$$

Since erosion is caused by repetitive loading, eventually leading to failure in the material, rain erosion is considered a fatigue problem. Coating materials and leading edge protection (LEP) systems are commonly tested using a rain erosion tester (RET) with a whirling arm setup, following industrial standards and recommendations [32–34]. The fatigue strength of the material is characterized by fitting the standard S-N-curve, i.e., cycle stress (S) vs. number of cycles (N). In rain erosion testing, the stress parameter is the impact velocity and the number of cycles can be represented by different metrics, e.g., kinetic impact energy, specific number of impacts, or accumulated impingement that we will be using. Following this approach, the allowed accumulated rain impingement before fatigue life can be associated with the impact velocity as:

$$H_{\text{allowed}} = c \cdot V_{\text{impact}}^{-m} \quad (10)$$

where c and m are the coefficient of the linear S-N-curve (see Appendix C for details on the fitting procedure). It should be mentioned that in this context, fatigue life refers to the end-of-incubation of the coating/LEP material, i.e., the period until the first visible damage. The terms fatigue life and end-of-incubation will be used interchangeably.

Combining Eq. (8) and (10), the incremental damage associated with the rain and wind characteristics, wind turbine rotor speed, and coating material can simply be expressed as the relative consumption of fatigue life:

$$\Delta D = \frac{H}{H_{\text{allowed}}} \quad (11)$$

Considering a whole range of wind speed and rain intensity, the linear damage accumulation can be obtained following the Palmgren–Miner summation rule. Similarly, if the joint probability distribution $f(U, I)$ of wind speed U and rain intensity I is known, the probability-weighted damage increment can be used to calculate the end-of-incubation or fatigue life L by simple integration:

$$L = \frac{1}{\int_{U,I} \Delta D \cdot f_{U,I}} \quad (12)$$

Having an analytical expression, we can derive the statistical moments, namely the mean and variance of the end-of-incubation.

As shown, the rain impingement is highly dependent on the impact velocity which is primarily dominated by the rotor speed of the turbine. In this study, we will use three different reference wind turbines with different operational characteristics as summarized in Table 1. These reference turbines will allow for assessing the sensitivity to increasing maximum tip speeds.

3.3. Erosion-safe operation

Erosion-safe operation (ESO) involves reducing the rotational speed of wind turbines during periods of heavy rain [29]. The objective of the ESO is to significantly minimize erosion damage while limiting the loss of energy production. Ideally, such a control strategy is optimized to maximize overall revenue, however, achieving this can be

Table 1
Operational characteristics of the reference wind turbines [35–37].

	Unit	NREL 5 MW	DTU 10 MW	IEA 15 MW
Rated power	[MW]	5	10	15
Rotor diameter	[m]	126	178.3	240
Hub height	[m]	90	119	150
Cut-in wind speed	[m/s]	3	4	3
Rated wind speed	[m/s]	11.4	11.4	10.6
Cut-out wind speed	[m/s]	25	25	25
Min. rotor speed	[rpm]	6.9	6	5
Max. rotor speed	[rpm]	12.1	9.6	7.56
Max. tip speed	[m/s]	80	90	95

challenging due to the complexity of the electricity market dynamics and the reliance on simplified cost models [38,39]. The ESO can potentially reduce the frequency of repairs and extend the intervals between inspections and maintenance. This approach not only improves blade reliability but also lowers downtime and (scheduled/unscheduled) repair costs, ultimately contributing to reduced operation and maintenance expenses.

The ESO control strategy is defined as a functional relationship between the rotor speed set-point and various independent variables, such as wind speed, rain intensity, droplet size, electricity price, or the current erosion damage of the blade. In this study, we focus exclusively on wind speed and rain intensity as the independent variables determining the rotor speed set-point. We then evaluate the efficiency of ESO η_{ESO} , defined as the extension in fatigue lifetime relative to the associated loss in annual energy production (AEP):

$$\eta_{\text{ESO}} = \frac{\Delta D}{\Delta \text{AEP}_{\text{loss}}} \quad (13)$$

High ESO efficiency is generally favorable, as it indicates good feasibility. However, it does not account for the original expected lifetime, e.g., ESO might be unnecessary if the blade lifetime is already expected to be sufficiently long, even if the ESO efficiency is high.

3.4. Evaluation metrics

To assess the goodness-of-fit of the fitted distribution, we employ the Kolmogorov–Smirnov (KS) test statistic, the coefficient of determination (R^2), and the root-mean-square error (RMSE) [40]. The R^2 and RMSE metrics are computed for the quantiles to evaluate the agreement between the empirical and fitted distributions. The metrics are implemented using SciPy and defined as follows:

$$D_n = \sup_x |F_n(x) - F(x)| \quad (14)$$

where D_n is the KS statistic, $F_n(x)$ is the empirical CDF, and $F(x)$ is the CDF of the fitted distribution.

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (Q_i^{\text{obs}} - Q_i^{\text{pred}})^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n (Q_i^{\text{obs}} - \bar{Q}^{\text{obs}})^2} \quad (15)$$

where Q_i^{obs} and Q_i^{pred} are the observed and predicted quantiles, respectively, and \bar{Q}^{obs} is the mean of the observed quantiles.

$$\text{RMSE} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (Q_i^{\text{obs}} - Q_i^{\text{pred}})^2} \quad (16)$$

where n is the number of quantiles, Q_i^{obs} are the observed quantiles, and Q_i^{pred} are the predicted quantiles.

4. Results

4.1. Distributional fitting

4.1.1. Marginal distributions

For both wind speed and rain intensity, we tested three different continuous, unimodal distributions. For wind speed, the Weibull,

Table 2

Summary of the fitting results from the marginal distributions of wind speed and rain intensity. The RMSE is measured in [m/s] for the wind speed distributions and in [mm/hr] for the rain intensity.

Variable	Distribution	K-S test	R^2	RMSE
Wind speed	Weibull	0.022	0.997	0.303
	Rayleigh	0.086	0.984	1.366
	Gamma	0.061	0.963	1.310
Rain intensity	Log-normal	0.040	0.987	1.366
	GEV	0.033	0.992	0.133
	Power log-normal	0.028	0.991	0.137

Table 3

Summary of the fitting results from the copula.

Copula family	K-S test	R^2	RMSE
Frank	0.026	0.998	0.332
Clayton	0.026	0.998	0.331
Gumbel	0.026	0.998	0.334

Rayleigh, and Gamma distributions were evaluated. To ensure physicality and eliminate the probability of negative wind speeds, only two-parameter distributions were used, with the location parameter fixed to zero. For rain intensity, we tested the log-normal, generalized extreme value (GEV), and power log-normal distributions. An initial log-transformation of rain intensity prior to fitting improved overall performance statistics.

The marginal distributions were fitted across the entire domain using maximum likelihood estimation (MLE). Goodness-of-fit was quantified using the Kolmogorov–Smirnov (K–S) test, supplemented by the R^2 -value and root-mean-square error (RMSE) of the theoretical versus empirical quantiles. The statistical evaluation of these fits is summarized in Table 2, with examples of quantile–quantile (QQ) plots for individual fits provided in Appendix A.

The Weibull distribution is observed as the best fit for wind speed, showing better performance across all metrics. The fitting error mainly occurred at high wind speeds, where theoretical quantiles were overestimated. However, this error region lies outside the typical operational regime and is therefore not expected to significantly impact results.

Rain intensity distributions were evaluated in the log-transformed space, where performance statistics were observed to be more comparable. Both the GEV and power log-normal distributions show the lowest RMSE. However, qualitative assessment of QQ-plots indicated that the GEV distribution better captured the high rain intensity regime compared to the power log-normal distribution.

4.1.2. Copula functions

We now evaluate the copulas based on the fitted marginal distributions. Three common copulas from the Archimedean family — the Gumbel, Clayton, and Frank copulas — are tested, as these one-parameter copulas are well-suited for bivariate distributions [41]. The copulas are fitted using MLE, with the copula function formulations provided in Appendix B. We assess the copulas using the same quantitative statistics applied to the marginals. The results are summarized in Table 3. Generally, the three copulas are all able to capture the dependence structure very well with very similar performance.

In addition to evaluating the statistical performance of the copulas, we conduct a qualitative assessment by comparing end-of-incubation estimates obtained from bootstrap sampling of the historical data with those derived from the fitted copulas. Due to the computational cost of bootstrap sampling, the comparison is limited to 100 randomly selected grid points, rather than the full domain of 15,600 coordinates. Convergence of the bootstrap lifetime estimate is ensured by running the method until the change in mean is $\leq 10^{-6}$. The error distribution between the bootstrap and copula-based end-of-incubation estimates is shown in Fig. 2 for the three copulas. While bootstrap sampling can be

Fig. 2. Distributions of the error between end-of-incubation estimates from bootstrap sampling and the three tested copulas.

Table 4

Summary of the probabilistic variables included in the erosion parameter atlas, including their distribution, number of parameters and available level heights.

Variable	Distribution	No. of parameters	Level heights
Annual rain frequency	Normal	2	–
Wind speed	Weibull	2	75, 100, 150 m
Rain intensity	GEV	3	–
Copula	Frank	1	75, 100, 150 m

flawed, as it assumes the historical data fully represents the distribution, it does allow for inter-comparison between the three copulas. The results indicate that the Frank copula outperforms the others, showing lower bias and a more Gaussian-like error distribution. In contrast, both the Clayton and Gumbel copulas exhibit slight skewness, with the Frank copula ultimately chosen for the final parameter atlas.

4.2. Erosion parameter atlas

With the final marginal distributions and copula selected, the full erosion parameter atlas is generated by applying the fitting procedure to all 15,600 grid points in the domain. This involved downloading historical wind and rain time series, fitting marginal distributions and copulas at each grid point, and storing the fitted parameters. This process was performed on an HPC cluster using 24 nodes, each with 2 ×AMD EPYC 7351 (16 cores per node, 128 GB RAM). The total computation time was approximately 4 h for the full domain. The subsequent applications of the fitted parameter atlas were performed on a laptop (Intel Core i7-1185G7, 32 GB RAM) and executed within minutes.

The parameter atlas allows for easy and flexible extraction of probabilistic features, such as conditional distributions or joint cumulative density functions. The variables included in the final erosion parameter atlas, along with their respective distributions, are summarized in Table 4.

A key variable in the erosion atlas is the probability of rain occurrence, representing the proportion of rainy or wet samples over an entire year. The normal distribution allows for including the inter-annual variability of rain. Practically, it is used to scale the joint probability density function for lifetime estimates, while its variance contributes to the overall uncertainty in these calculations. The mean probability of rain occurrence across the domain is shown in Fig. 3. It shows that the rain is most frequent in western coastal regions, particularly around the islands west and north of Scotland, as well as the peninsulas of the southwest coast of Wales and England. These hotspots are influenced by a combination of orographic effects and

Fig. 3. Mean annual rain frequency across studied domain covering the British Isles and surrounding seas based on IMERG precipitation data.

exposure to Atlantic weather systems, including low-pressure patterns driven by westerly winds.

From the erosion parameter atlas, we can also directly evaluate the marginal distributions individually or conditionally. As an example, we can visualize how the wind speed changes conditioned on the rain intensity. Fig. 4 shows the normalized wind speed as function of rain intensity. The graph is based on 1000 randomly selected coordinates. Notice that the rain intensity starts at 0.1 mm/hr and not at 0 mm/hr. A clear trend is observed highlighting, not just the co-occurrence of wind and rain, but also the overall positive correlation between the two. Generally, the wind speed is expected to be 5%–25% higher when it is raining 10 mm/hr compared to 0.1 mm/hr. This effect is even more significant when it is not raining at all, with the average wind speed being 50% higher when it is raining 10 mm/hr compared to no rain.

Another feature of the probability-based erosion parameter atlas is the ability to visualize the marginal distributions individually. When examining the quantiles of rain intensity (Fig. 5), we observe a much more distinct change in appearance across the three quantiles. Particularly, the highest 50th percentiles are located in Great Britain, while the highest 95th percentile shifts to southwest Ireland. This feature highlights the complex spatial variability of rain intensity distribution, suggesting that simple metrics like annual rainfall may not always serve as adequate proxies for assessing erosion risk. For wind speed, the three quantiles show greater similarity in appearance, with offshore regions generally having higher wind speeds, and local orographic features distinctly influencing the spatial patterns. These observations also highlight the differences in how rain intensity and wind speed distributions vary spatially and across quantiles.

The most distinctive feature of the erosion parameter atlas is the dependence structure captured by the copula parameter θ . This parameter directly quantifies the significance of the statistical dependence

Fig. 4. Normalized wind speed conditioned on rain intensity. The shaded area indicates the 95% interval with the median shown by the solid black line.

between the two variables, i.e., wind speed and rain intensity. It is closely related to rank correlation coefficients such as Kendall's τ and Spearman's ρ . The spatial distribution of the copula parameter is visualized in Fig. 6.

The results show that there is a prevailing positive dependence structure across the entire domain, indicating an enhanced co-occurrence of wind and rain. These findings align with those shown from Fig. 4, which demonstrate that wind speeds tend to be stronger during rainfall and increase further as rain intensity grows. The copula parameter is notably higher in coastal regions, areas of particular

Fig. 5. Maps of the 50th, 75th and 95th percentiles of wind speed (top row) and rain intensity (bottom row) across the studied geographical domain.

Fig. 6. Map showing the fitted copula parameter across the studied geographical domain. The red dots indicate the location of two coordinates with comparable mean wind speed and annual rainfall, but different statistical dependence structure.

Fig. 7. Comparison of accumulated rain impingement for two sites with comparable mean wind speed and annual rainfall but (left) low dependence between wind speed and rain intensity, and (right) high dependence between wind speed and rain intensity.

interest for offshore wind farms. These results further motivates the need for assessing local dependence structures when conducting erosion risk assessment.

4.3. Accumulated rain impingement

As described in Section 3.2, rain impingement is an important predictor for the leading edge erosion that is used in several damage models. The accumulated rain impingement can be calculated using Eq. (8) and is highly dependent on the co-occurrence of wind and rain as well as turbine characteristics. Fig. 7 shows a time series of the accumulated rain impingement. The plots are generated for two selected sites, as shown in Fig. 6, which have a comparable average wind speed of 12 m/s and annual rainfall of 1483 mm and 1471 mm for the low- and high-dependence sites, respectively, but exhibit very different dependence structures. The high-dependence site experiences more than 30% higher accumulated rain impingement relative to the low-dependence site. This effect can be attributed to the co-occurrence of wind and rain that is captured through the copula. The probabilistic capability of the erosion parameter atlas is also demonstrated through the shaded area which captures the combined aleatory uncertainty coming from the natural variation of the wind and rain. The uncertainty is constituted of the natural variation coming from the probability of rain and the joint distribution of wind and rain. The mean and standard deviation of the accumulated rain impingement was found to be 34.6 ± 1.7 m/yr for the low-dependence site and 46.2 ± 2.5 m/yr for the high-dependence site. It was found that the major attribute of the uncertainty comes from the variation in the probability of rain, between 80%–90% for both sites.

Since the joint distribution is typically accumulated over several years, the relative uncertainty will naturally converge following the law of large numbers. This was further supported by assessing the historical data used for fitting, which showed that the inter-annual distribution of rain and wind was very similar but the major difference was the frequency of rainy periods. Finally, we observe how the larger turbines will increasingly experience a higher accumulated rain impingement due to the increased tip speed. The IEA 15 MW reference turbine would experience approximately 12 and 23% higher accumulated rain impingement per year compared to the DTU 10 MW and NREL 5 MW reference turbines, respectively, for both sites.

4.4. End-of-incubation estimates

The damage model used to calculate the end-of-incubation requires parametrization of the coating material, as detailed in Section 3.2. To derive the linear coefficients, we use experimental data from [28]. The tested specimens were constructed by infusing epoxy into a 12-layer bi-axial glass fiber layup. The top coating was a commercial polyurethane (PU) coating designed for high erosion resistance.

Since the coating parametrization relies on linear fitting, and the industrial standards for fitting such a curve do not include adequate recommendations on how to properly include uncertainty. In this paper, we implement Bayesian linear regression [42], which is a linear regression method that incorporates Bayesian inference to estimate a probabilistic model, applying priors to the coefficients to prevent overfitting and quantify uncertainty. The details for the full fitting procedure can be found in Appendix C. The deterministic best-fit coefficients from Eq. (10) were found as $c = 3.56 \cdot 10^{20}$ and $m = 9.58$, corresponding very well with the parameters found in the original publication [28].

Using these coefficients, the end-of-incubation was predicted following the procedure in Section 3.2. Fig. 8 presents spatial variations in end-of-incubation across the domain for the three reference wind turbines. The maps reveal significant differences in erosion onset depending on turbine size and location. For the NREL 5 MW turbine, the incubation periods are the longest, exceeding 40 years in some inland regions, particularly in areas with relatively low wind speeds. The DTU 10 MW turbine exhibits shorter end-of-incubation periods, with maximum values around 12 years. The IEA 15 MW turbine shows the shortest fatigue life, with incubation periods falling below 4 years in many areas, especially offshore and in wind-intensive zones. Across all three turbines, a clear spatial pattern emerges, with offshore and western coastal regions consistently showing shorter end-of-incubation periods compared to inland areas. The reduction in incubation with increasing turbine size is caused by the correspondingly higher tip speeds. This also indicates to what extent modern wind turbines can expect in terms of incubation and highlights the sensitivity to the maximum tip speed.

As shown, the erosion parameter atlas enables the calculation of the end-of-incubation by appropriately accounting for the dependence structure between wind speed and rain intensity. Additionally, because the atlas provides the marginal distributions, it is also possible to compute the corresponding incubation period assuming only the independent marginal distributions. Fig. 9 illustrates the ratio between the incubation calculated from the independent marginals and those obtained from the joint distribution modeled with a copula.

The map is visualized specifically for the IEA 15 MW reference turbine. The results indicate that the ratio ranges from 1.1 to 1.9, corresponding to a likely overestimation of the end-of-incubation by 10%–90% when the independent marginal distributions are used instead of the joint distribution. On average, the overestimation across the entire domain is 45%. Spatial variability in the error is evident, with localized regions of higher and lower discrepancies. Notably, the western and southern regions of Great Britain exhibit relatively higher overestimation errors, while the northeastern region is characterized by comparatively lower errors. These findings emphasizes the importance of incorporating the full dependence structure in erosion modeling to avoid substantial errors, particularly in regions with high co-occurrence.

Fig. 8. Maps of the end-of-incubation for three different wind turbine types.

Fig. 9. Map showing the ratio between end-of-incubation period estimated using copula (dependent) and individual marginals (independent).

Furthermore, we can evaluate how this overestimation error is directly related to the dependence structure. Fig. 10 visualizes the percentage error in end-of-incubation as function of the copula parameter. A general clustering pattern is visible, which can be attributed to the spatial coherence of the environmental conditions across different regions, as certain sites share similar weather characteristics. A clear positive trend is observed between the copula parameter and the error in incubation estimate. As mentioned, the copula parameter represents

the dependence structure and measures how strongly the wind speed and rain intensity are related. Stronger dependence between wind and rain leads to larger errors.

4.5. Reliability analysis

Next, we will use the capability of the erosion parameter atlas in combination with the fitting of the experimental rain erosion test data.

Fig. 10. Scatter plot showing the percentage error in end-of-incubation estimated using copula (dependent) and individual marginals (independent) as a function of the copula parameter.

Since the Bayesian linear regression allows for deriving the posterior distribution of the two coating parameters, and we have the joint distribution of wind and rain as provided by the copula and marginals, we can calculate the full probabilistic end-of-incubation. We do this using Monte Carlo methods, which are run until statistical convergence is reached i.e., the change in both mean and variance is less than a tolerance value of 10^{-6} . As previously, we compare the two selected sites (see Fig. 6 with comparable mean wind speed and annual rainfall, but low- and high-dependence). The results are shown in Fig. 11 and compares the distribution of the end-of-incubation. The left figure shows the probability density functions of the end-of-incubation for the low-dependence site (blue curve) and the high-dependence site (red curve). The site with high-dependence exhibits a sharply peaked distribution, indicating shorter end-of-incubation with less variability, while the low-dependence site is broader and shifted toward higher end-of-incubation, suggesting more durability. The shaded regions under the curves highlight the proportion of blades with end-of-incubation exceeding 3 years; only 10% for the high-dependence site compared to 47% for the low-dependence site. This contrast highlights the significant influence of the dependence structure on coating performance, even when the sites have comparable mean wind speed and average annual rainfall. The right panel presents the corresponding survival functions, representing the likelihood that coatings last longer than a given period. Again, we can see that the low-dependence site exhibits a slower decline, with 47% of coatings having an incubation period of more than 3 years, whereas the high-dependence site shows a rapid decrease, with only 10% surviving beyond the same threshold. These results support the findings that the statistical dependence structure has a pronounced impact on coating durability, significantly affecting the incubation period. Together, the density and survival functions allow for assessing the site-specific reliability of a given coating which can be an important tool for material design and maintenance strategies.

4.6. Erosion-safe operation efficiency

In this section, we will evaluate how efficiently ESO can be implemented, i.e., by evaluating the potential erosion damage reduction (equivalent to lifetime extension) against the corresponding loss in energy production. ESO can either be implemented using a power stop-loss or lifetime target. The purpose of the power stop-loss is to achieve the highest extension in life using a maximum allowed power or AEP loss. The lifetime target strategy on the other hand, implements the ESO such that a specific target life is obtained without considering the AEP loss. The power stop-loss strategy was implemented for the

IEA 15 MW reference turbine. A maximum allowed AEP loss of 1% was chosen and the corresponding extension in erosion lifetime was computed. As was shown in Fig. 11, the probabilistic fatigue lifetime can vary significantly, and for that reason, the ESO efficiency will also vary. For practical reasons, we use the average fatigue lifetime and AEP loss to derive the ESO strategy. The results are visualized in Fig. 12 for all coordinates, which shows the ratio of fatigue life extension associated with a 1% loss in AEP. A value of two indicates a doubling in erosion life. It should be mentioned, that the ESO efficiency is also dependent on the tip speed and power curve of the specific turbine, particularly the rated wind speed.

5. Discussion

This study aims to provide an alternative framework for modeling and analyzing the risks related to leading edge erosion on wind turbine blades using a probabilistic approach. The particular focus is on the joint behavior and co-occurrence of wind and rain, and their impact on coating fatigue life. While the proposed methodology offers certain advancements in assessing erosion risk, several elements benefit from a discussion to better understand the limitations, assumptions, and potential future applications.

One of the main considerations when developing the erosion parameter atlas is the selection of a representative domain and time period. The accuracy and statistical properties of any parametric distributional fit are highly dependent on the data it is based on, making it critical to ensure that the chosen domain accurately represents the geographical and climatic conditions of interest. In the present study, we use historical data from a limited geographical domain and it is important to recognize that these data, while useful, may not fully capture the diversity of wind and rain interactions present in other weather systems or geographical regions. As an example, in tropical regions influenced by monsoons or cyclones, or in arid zones where rainfall occurs as isolated and intense downbursts, the joint behavior of wind and rain may differ substantially. For that reason, extending the framework to other regions would require new evaluations of the goodness-of-fit for the different marginal distributions and copulas.

The historical data used in this study for generating the erosion parameter atlas is limited to only five years. Such a relatively short period of time may not be enough to capture long-term climatic conditions which would typically require decades of historical data. Similarly, historical data does not account for general trends or future changes in weather extremes, e.g., those related to climate change. As extreme events such as heavy rainfall and high winds are expected to become more frequent or intense, relying solely on historical data could lead to inaccurate parametrization of the coupled wind and rain climate, therefore also the potential erosion risk in the future. Ultimately, the distributional fits used in this study are never better than the data they are based on, which introduces a degree of uncertainty to the results. Future research could benefit from considering longer time horizons or adjusting the models based on updated climate projections to better account for changing patterns in weather extremes.

The historical data used in the study was obtained from two different data products, namely the NWEA and IMERG. The assumption underlying the synchronization process is that the temporal resolutions of the two datasets are sufficiently aligned to represent coinciding wind and rain events at the same time and location. However, these datasets are derived from fundamentally different sources, i.e., NWEA relies on mesoscale weather models and ground observations, while IMERG integrates satellite observations with gauge-corrected precipitation estimates. Even though both datasets provide high temporal resolution, their reporting times and methods for deriving observations may differ slightly, e.g., satellite observations from IMERG involve processing delays and spatial averaging that may not align perfectly with the modeled wind fields in NWEA, particularly during rapidly evolving weather conditions such as storms.

Fig. 11. Reliability analysis comparing the probabilistic incubation period of two sites with comparable mean wind speed and annual rainfall but different dependence structure. The left figure shows the probability distribution of the end-of-incubation and the right figure shows the corresponding survival function.

Fig. 12. Map showing the ratio of fatigue life extension that would be obtained with an AEP loss of 1%. The simulation is run for the IEA 15 MW reference turbine.

The consequences of these potential mismatches can have a significant impact on the results. If there is even a small temporal offset between the datasets, the joint distribution of wind and rain could be distorted, leading to an inaccurate representation of their co-occurrence. As an example, rain events recorded in IMERG might not coincide with the peak wind speeds recorded in NEWA, resulting in an underestimation of the erosion potential during specific events. This could affect the fitting of the marginals and copula, leading to biased estimates of the dependency structure and unreliable estimates of the incubation period.

Future studies could validate the synchronization against independent ground-truth data when available. Additionally, sensitivity analyses could be conducted to assess the impact of small temporal offsets on the results. Interests would also be in exploring the use of data from a single source or using advanced synchronization techniques such as dynamic time warping to improve the alignment of wind and rain events.

We have implemented Bayesian linear regression to fit the experimental data from the rain erosion tester. This is a robust alternative to the ordinary least squares method commonly recommended in industry standards. As mentioned, Bayesian regression captures the full

posterior distribution of derived coating parameters, enabling a more comprehensive assessment of uncertainty. By providing probabilistic coating parameter estimates, the Bayesian approach integrates very well with the rest of the probabilistic framework used in this study and offers flexibility in terms of different material types or experimental setups. Bayesian linear regression provides a powerful tool for improving the reliability analysis of the erosion fatigue life. The authors recommend that future studies incorporate similar uncertainty estimates when working with experimental data from rain erosion testers as the inherently stochastic nature of leading edge erosion demands a probabilistic approach. This allows for a more comprehensive and realistic representation of material behavior.

The study also provides a demonstration of how ESO could be implemented based on either restricting the loss in AEP or setting an incubation period target. As mentioned, the results related to this rely on mean estimates for AEP loss and lifetime extension, but a conditional probabilistic approach could also be employed. As an example, the ESO strategy should ensure that a minimum proportion (e.g., 80%) of blades would satisfy the desired conditions. This probabilistic approach would better capture the variability and ensure that the ESO implementation remains robust across a range of possible operational conditions.

For wind farm control, it would also be necessary to account for wind direction when developing and evaluating ESO strategies. This could be achieved by extending the copula framework to include wind direction using vine copulas with a mixture of von Mises models as in [18].

The efficiency of ESO is also expected to be significantly improved when using higher temporal resolution data. In this study, the analysis is based on 30 min data, which inherently smooths the peaks of rain intensity and wind speed compared to e.g., 1 min data. Higher-resolution data would better capture the true variability of extreme events, making ESO strategies able to target these periods more accurately. Additionally, for real-life implementation, the relevant instrumentation for tracking rain and wind would already operate at a higher temporal resolution.

Finally, while AEP is a useful metric for evaluating ESO efficiency, it is not the most relevant measure from a financial perspective. AEP is not linearly correlated with revenue, which is often influenced by the electricity market. Wind speeds and electricity prices are typically positively correlated, and because ESO primarily targets high wind speeds, the actual loss in revenue may be smaller than the corresponding AEP loss. This suggests that the perceived revenue loss of ESO might be overestimated if only AEP is considered. Using a revenue-based metric would enable a more realistic valuation of lifetime extension through net present value calculations, offering a clearer assessment of long-term financial returns. However, this perspective assumes a zero-subsidy scenario, where revenue directly depends on market electricity prices. For asset operations with subsidies or fixed tariffs, this relationship would need further exploration.

Fig. A.13. Example of a single QQ-plot for the three wind speed distributions. The statistics are shown for each distribution.

Fig. A.14. Example of a single QQ-plot for the three rain intensity distributions. The statistics are shown for each distribution. The physical value have been log-transformed for better representation.

The results of this study demonstrate that the incubation period is significantly reduced for larger turbines with higher tip speeds, emphasizing that the operational characteristics are of great importance when assessing erosion risk. New turbines are becoming increasingly larger, with rotor diameters approaching 200 meters in some cases, and tip speeds exceeding 100 m/s (e.g. the Vestas V236-15.0MW with a design tip speed of 104 m/s). This makes it more important to assess the full reliability of a specific coating in relation to the turbine and site-specific conditions. A detailed understanding of how environmental conditions, turbine operation, and coating properties interact is essential for ensuring the durability of wind turbine components and minimizing maintenance costs over their operational lifetime.

It is important to mention that the approach presented in this study is primarily intended for statistical purposes, rather than direct predictive modeling based on historical data. The probabilistic erosion parameter atlas is particularly well-suited for the design phase of wind farms, where understanding the long-term erosion risks and durability of coatings is crucial. During the design, it can be used to assess potential risks under varying environmental conditions, enabling the selection of appropriate materials. However, the approach is less applicable for already operating wind farms, where real-time data and ongoing maintenance activities play a more significant role in managing erosion.

The framework allows for the substitution of alternative data sources, including regional or global climate datasets, high-frequency weather station measurements, or outputs from other numerical weather prediction models. This modularity of the distributional fitting procedure and subsequent applications makes it very flexible. Additionally, the probabilistic nature of the model accommodates the inherent uncertainty in weather data, making it suitable for datasets of varying quality or resolution. Beyond its application to different data sources, the framework can also be extended to incorporate alternative fatigue lifetime models. While this study employs specific erosion metrics based on accumulated rain impingement and material fatigue characteristics, the methodology can easily be adapted to other models, As an example,

the end-of-incubation estimates are particularly relevant in testing new materials, providing insights into their performance under controlled conditions. Future work could expand the framework to include other levels of damage, such as those commonly used in the industry to determine the need for repair, enabling more comprehensive assessments. This adaptability allows for addressing a broad range of research and practical needs, from site-specific turbine optimization to large-scale erosion risk mapping. This study provides a scalable tool that can support both academic research and industry applications in wind turbine design and maintenance planning.

6. Conclusions

This study highlights the importance of modeling the statistical dependence between wind speed and rain intensity for accurately assessing leading edge erosion risks in wind turbines. Conventional fatigue lifetime models, which typically assume independence between these variables, can significantly misrepresent site-specific erosion risks. By employing copulas, we capture their dependence structure, enabling a more accurate and flexible probabilistic framework for erosion assessment.

Using historical wind and rain data from the British Isles and surrounding seas, we fitted the most suitable marginal probability distributions and copula function. The resulting probabilistic erosion risk atlas provides a powerful tool for rapid site-specific assessments, supporting custom reliability analyses based on turbine operation, blade coating properties, and local climate conditions. It also facilitates the evaluation of erosion-safe operation strategies, aiding in their feasibility assessment and optimization.

Results indicate that ignoring wind-rain dependence can overestimate the incubation period by up to 90%, particularly in offshore and coastal regions, where wind and rain are strongly correlated. During intense rainfall (10 mm/hr), wind speeds are on average 50% higher than in dry conditions, emphasizing the critical role of wind-rain interactions in erosion modeling. Additionally, turbines operating

Table B.5

Definitions of the three Archimedean copulas used in the study.

Copula family	$C(U, V; \theta)$
Frank	$-\frac{1}{\theta} \ln \left(1 + \frac{(e^{-\theta U} - 1)(e^{-\theta V} - 1)}{e^{-\theta} - 1} \right), \quad \theta \neq 0$
Clayton	$\max \left\{ (U^{-\theta} + V^{-\theta} - 1)^{-\frac{1}{\theta}}, 0 \right\}, \quad \theta > 0$
Gumbel	$\exp \left(- \left[(-\ln U)^\theta + (-\ln V)^\theta \right]^{\frac{1}{\theta}} \right), \quad \theta \geq 1$

at higher tip speeds reach the end-of-incubation significantly faster, underscoring the need for accurate erosion risk assessment, especially for the new generation of larger turbines. The erosion parameter atlas further enables site-specific evaluations of erosion-safe operation strategies. Results reveal substantial regional variability, with some inland areas showing the potential to extend the incubation period by up to 500%, requiring only a 1% reduction in annual energy production.

Future research should incorporate variable droplet size distributions to refine impact energy estimates as well as seasonal effects to capture periodic variations in erosion risk. Higher spatial and temporal resolution in datasets would further improve local-scale accuracy, while validating the framework with real-world erosion data remains a key step in establishing its predictive reliability and industry applicability.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Jens Visbeck: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Software, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Charlotte Bay Hasager:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition. **Tuhfe Göçmen:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration. **Pierre-Elouan Réthoré:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration.

Declaration of generative AI in scientific writing

Assistance of ChatGPT as the AI/LLM for editing and grammar enhancement is used in parts of this work to improve general readability and language. The output of the AI is carefully reviewed and integrated by the authors to ensure accuracy, relevance, and alignment with the presented study.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Marginal distributions

See Fig. A.13 and Fig. A.14.

Appendix B. Copula formulations

See Table B.5.

Fig. C.15. Experimental data conducted from a whirling-arm rain erosion tester (RET) provided by [28]. Bayesian linear regression has been used to fit the fatigue curve to the experimental data (black dots). The best-fit is shown by the red line and the 95% prediction interval by the blue shaded area.

Appendix C. Bayesian linear regression for VN-curve fitting

To fit a linear SN-curve (Wöhler curve) using Bayesian linear regression, we model the relationship between the stress amplitude S and the number of cycles to failure N as:

$$\log N = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \log S + \epsilon \quad (C.1)$$

where β_0 and β_1 are the regression coefficients, and ϵ represents the noise term.

Assume a prior for the coefficients $\beta = (\beta_0, \beta_1)^T$ as:

$$p(\beta) = \mathcal{N}(\beta; \mu_0, \Sigma_0) \quad (C.2)$$

where μ_0 is the prior mean and Σ_0 is the prior covariance matrix.

The likelihood of the observed data $\{(S_i, N_i)\}$ given the model is:

$$p(y_i | \beta) = \mathcal{N}(y_i; \beta_0 + \beta_1 \log S_i, \sigma^2) \quad (C.3)$$

where $y_i = \log N_i$, and σ^2 is the noise variance.

Using Bayes' theorem, the posterior distribution of the coefficients is:

$$p(\beta | y, X) \propto p(y | X, \beta) p(\beta) \quad (C.4)$$

where $X = \{\log S_i\}$ are the explanatory variables, and $y = \{\log N_i\}$ are the responses.

The posterior distribution of the coefficients β can be used to quantify uncertainty in the model parameters. The posterior mean $\hat{\beta}$ and covariance matrix $\hat{\Sigma}$ are obtained by solving the following system:

$$\hat{\beta} = (\Sigma_0^{-1} + X^T X / \sigma^2)^{-1} (\Sigma_0^{-1} \mu_0 + X^T y / \sigma^2) \quad (C.5)$$

$$\hat{\Sigma} = (\Sigma_0^{-1} + X^T X / \sigma^2)^{-1} \quad (C.6)$$

This posterior distribution provides a full probabilistic description of the regression coefficients, allowing for uncertainty quantification in predictions of the SN-curve. Fig. C.15 shows experimental data from a rain erosion tester with the best-fit coefficients shown and indicated by the red line. The 95% prediction interval obtained from the posterior distribution of the parameters is indicated by the shaded area.

Data availability

The data products used for this study are freely available via <https://map.neweuropeanwindatlas.eu/> (NEWA) and [https://disc.gsfc.nasa.gov/datasets/GPM_3IMERGHH_07/summary?keywords=22IMERG20final22\(IMERG\)](https://disc.gsfc.nasa.gov/datasets/GPM_3IMERGHH_07/summary?keywords=22IMERG20final22(IMERG))

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